

Research sheet of Turemugo Lab

Volume 4

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2025

Erratum to the *Leucoagaricus-Leucocoprinus* article (Yang *et al.* 2024): Lepiotaceae should not be validated, and an earlier, legitimate name Verrucosporaceae Jülich 1982 should be adopted instead

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Citation Yang, K.L. 2025. Erratum to the *Leucoagaricus-Leucocoprinus* article (Yang *et al.* 2024): Lepiotaceae should not be validated, and an earlier, legitimate name Verrucosporaceae Jülich 1982 should be adopted instead. *Research sheet of Turemugo Lab* (posted on Zenodo) 4(2): 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14665428>

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Friendly Reminder These contents may become outdated following future academic progress. Please keep an eye on the latest researches.

Text

Dear colleagues,

Thanks to the kind reminder of Jacob Kalichman (University of Tennessee at Knoxville), I do notice a mistake in a recent work first-authored by me, regarding the validation of a family name—*Lépiotées* Roze, *Bulletin de la Société botanique de France* 23: 111 (1876):

Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M., Li, T.H. & Yang, Z.L. 2024. Rediscovering *Leucoagaricus sinicus*, with the recognition of *Leucoagaricus* and *Leucocoprinus* as separate genera, and two new genera in Agaricaceae (Basidiomycota). *Phytotaxa* 676(3): 199–255.

In this work, *Lépiotées* Roze was proposed to be validated as Lepiotaceae Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang, but currently Verrucosporaceae Jülich 1982 is the earlier and legitimate name, and Lepiotaceae Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang is legitimate but incorrect by Arts. 52.1 & 52.4. in the current code (Turland *et al.* 2018). Although there seems no available molecular data for the type material or collections from the type locality of *Verrucospora* to safely confirm the position of this genus, currently *Verrucospora* should be placed with *Lepiota* and its allies in a single family as revealed by the molecular phylogenetic position of some Asian collections identified as *Verrucospora* (e.g., HYW146 from Thailand (ITS OR035512), HNL502005 from Laos (ITS ON197329) & KUN-HKAS60233 from China (ITS MN810121)); see also the phylogeny in Yang *et al.* (2024), corrected as the Figure 1 below, called Verrucosporaceae but not Lepiotaceae, unless *Lépiotées* Roze is to be conserved, protected or sanctioned in the future, or the type of *Verrucospora* is to be proven as *Inocybe* or some others. It is my oversight that I ignored Verrucosporaceae as I did mainly focus on the work of Singer

(1986) while I was checking the potential synonyms of "Lepiotaceae". I'm deeply sorry about this issue in my work.

For other minor corrections to this work, please see Yang & Lin (2025).

▲ Figure 1. Current subdivisions within Agaricaceae s. l., a corrected version for the figure 1E in Yang et al. (2024). Chinese names are also attached.

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Suisuinians

团队所有人都忽视了疣孢环柄菇科的存在，同样忽视了它的似乎还有我们所关注的数篇重要节点文献的作者.. 随着分类学界发表的名称越来越多，将来创建新的高阶元名称需慎之又慎！我必须引以为戒